

**UNIVERSITY STUDENTS' DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES AND
THEIR ENTREPRENEURIAL BUSINESS VENTURE CHOICES IN
CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA: IMPLICATIONS FOR
MANAGEMENT EFFECTIVENESS**

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Abstract:

This study investigated the influence of University Students' Demographic Variables on their Entrepreneurial Business Venture Choices in Cross River State, Nigeria and its implication for management effectiveness. Two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 levels of significance. Survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised three thousand, nine hundred and sixty (3,960) final year students of nine (9) faculties from two universities (University of Calabar and Cross River University of Technology) in Cross River State. The sample was three hundred and ninety six (396) final year students drawn from the faculties through stratified random sampling technique. A researcher-developed questionnaire named "Students' Demographics and Entrepreneurial Business Venture Choice Questionnaire (SDEBVCQ)" was used for data collection. Contingency Chi-square analysis was used in testing the two hypotheses. Results of the analysis revealed that there is a significant influence of ethnic/geo-political and family business background on entrepreneurial business venture choices of university students. Based on these results, it was recommended that wide range of business choices should be provided in the entrepreneurial programme for students to choose from with emphasis on their demographics. The university system should device strategies to assist the students that

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indicated their intentions to start enterprises while in school and after graduation through incubation programmes.

Keywords: university students, demographic variables, entrepreneurship, management

1. Background to the study

Education globally is known to be an indispensable tool for socio-economic development and wealth creation. It is an instrument par excellence for effecting national development (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2004). The influence that education has on the attitudes and aspirations of youths depends on their understanding of the impact such education will have on their socio-economic wellbeing. For education to be potent and useful, it must have to be indigenized. That is to say, it must be designed in accordance with the prevailing needs of the society and the nation at large.

University education as prescribed by Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004,p.28) is meant to make optimum contribution to national development through:

- a. Intensifying and diversifying its programmes for the development of high level manpower within the context of the needs of the nation.
- b. Making professional course contents reflect our national requirements.
- c. Making all students part of a general programme of all-round improvement in university education, to offer general study courses such as History of Ideas, Philosophy of Knowledge, Nationalism and Information Technology.
- d. Making entrepreneurial skills acquisition a requirement for all Nigerian universities.

It is no gainsaying that some of the objectives of the Nigerian university education have become unfulfilled particularly in the area of diversifying for self-employment generation. The non-attainment of these objectives created a lot of social problems; significant among them is the quality and number of graduate output yearly and its multiplier effect of unemployment. Katsina (2010) frowned at the increasing involvement of youths in criminal activities in the country and called on government at all levels to initiate proactive curricular in the education system.

The state of unemployment across the country prompted federal government to direct all the tertiary education regulatory agencies to establish mechanism for the introduction, development and sustenance of entrepreneurial culture among Nigerian youths. Following the presidential directive through the Federal Ministry of Education, entrepreneurial studies was introduced and made compulsory for all students in higher

educational institutions in Nigeria effective from 2007/2008 academic session (Akuegwu & Udida, 2008; Yahaya, 2011).

Today, many universities in Nigeria including the University of Calabar as well as Cross River University of Technology have included entrepreneurial studies in their respective institution's curricular. This is an attempt to reverse graduate unemployment trend by giving needed training in entrepreneurial skills to students in their respective centres of training. Students who participated in entrepreneurial programmes from these two institutions and indeed graduate usually showcase their skills by engaging in various entrepreneurial business ventures within their institutions and around Calabar metropolis.

Entrepreneurship therefore, is the production of goods or provision of services for sale with the intention to make profit. Entrepreneurship and business are two familiar bedfellows and means the same thing (Oshorun, 2009). Accordingly, the word "business" formed part of the definition of entrepreneurship, meaning that business is an integral part of entrepreneurship. From the foregoing therefore, it could be said that entrepreneurship leads or culminates in business, as business constitutes the product of entrepreneurship. It is from the above analysis that Oshorun inferred that entrepreneurship is a parent while business is the offspring in the relationship. Without entrepreneurship, there cannot be a business; *"entrepreneurship is the fire while business is the smoke"*. Entrepreneurial business venture choice is the ability of an individual to pick any money yielding activity for the purpose of generating income based on knowledge, interest and capability.

There is a subsisting awareness among students of the efficacy of entrepreneurial studies as an instrument for socio-economic development and wealth creation in the University of Calabar and Cross River University of Technology. This is evident in their palpable willingness to engage in income yielding ventures like Catering, Fashion designing, Hairdressing, Computer repairs, Photography, and Fish farming among others. With the awareness and willingness however, it is hoped that students could be able to make specific choice of entrepreneurial business ventures that could serve as platforms for employment generation for themselves and others. Through this, they contribute towards reducing the rate of unemployment in the society and to the nation's Gross Domestic Product.

The study of entrepreneurship exposes students to number of business venture choices such as: Hairdressing, Fashion designing, Photography, Bread baking, Bead making, Computer repairs. Others are; Interior decoration, Electrical wiring, Fish farming and Painting. They are expected to choose any of these business ventures and specialize in it with the intention of plying it as a trade for employment purposes upon

their graduation. It is no contradiction however, that students who are exposed to entrepreneurial programme have the tendency to possess a better outlook in terms of their attitudes and aspirations.

Nigeria is a multi-ethnic country with each tribe having unique features - culturally, socially, religiously and educationally, that distinguishes her from others. Apart from these, there are the ethnic/geo-political and family background dimensions. Ethnic/geo-political background in this study means the tribe or geo-political area an individual comes from that may shape his/her choice of business venture. Family business background, in this study is a line of business activity a particular family does or is noted for. It is therefore, the intention of the researchers to investigate whether these factors influence students' entrepreneurship business venture choices in universities in Cross River State, Nigeria.

2. Statement of the problem

Nigerian youths, especially those in the universities and those who have graduated, have been experiencing uncertainty as a result of their inability to acquire entrepreneurial skills to engage themselves productively both individually and corporately. The result has been unbridled unemployment. In response to this anomaly, universities in Nigeria have embarked on entrepreneurship education. To determine the contributions of this education programme towards solving the problem of unemployment, a number of studies have been undertaken; none of which focused on demographic variables and entrepreneurial business venture choices. It is the consideration of the above problem that motivated the researchers to embark on this study. The problem of this study is therefore posed thus: How do demographic variables influence entrepreneurial business venture choices of university students in Cross River State, Nigeria?

2.1 Statement of hypotheses

1. There is no significant influence of ethnic/geo-political background on entrepreneurial business venture choices of university students.
2. There is no significant influence of family business background on entrepreneurial business venture choices of university students.

3. Literature Review

- Ethnic/geo-political background and entrepreneurial business venture choices
- Family business background and entrepreneurial business venture choices.

3.1 Ethnic/geo-political background and entrepreneurial business venture choices

Basu and Virick (2008) asserted that the role of ethnicity, as an antecedent of entrepreneurial intentions, could be explained through self-efficacy differences or differences in family and house hold characteristics, including human and financial capital across ethnic groups. Fairly (2004) reported that empirical research in US indicated significant differences in self-employment rates among different ethnic and racial groups. The study found that rising self-employment among Blacks between 1979 and 1998, and the narrowing gap between Black and White self-employment rates could be traced to increasing educational levels among Black men. In contrast, self-employment rates between Hispanics and Whites widened over the same period, and that trend was associated with no corresponding improvement in educational attainment of Hispanic men.

Ugwu and Ugwu (2012) stated that ethnicity/culture entails common values, belief system, and practices based on nationality, common ancestry, and/or common immigration experiences. Ethnic groups are culture-bearing units and common group values were major contributors to a sense of identity and to peculiar ways of perceiving, thinking, feeling and behaving that influenced action in everyday life (Chan & Lee, 2004; Hanson, 2004), including entrepreneurial intent and the actual entrepreneurial behaviour. Entrepreneurial activity in many societies was heavily influenced by cultural practices. While some cultures tend to stifle the independent thinking and creative ability, some other individual whose culture is supportive tend to be prolific in initiating ventures (Urban, 2006).

Studies by Kumar and Kelly (2006) indicated that an individual's cultural background determined how traits were exercised, practiced and manifested, which could be implicated in superior entrepreneurial intentions. Entrepreneurs could not act in a social vacuum, but were influenced by the background into which they were born as well as environment in which they were raised (Goksel & Aydintan, 2011). For instance, an assumption was often made that individual from the Igbo ethnic group in Nigeria exhibited the highest entrepreneurial tendencies (Ugwu & Ugwu, 2012), but this has remained largely untested.

Wilson, Marlino and Kickul (2004) found significant ethnic/racial and gender differences among students in terms of the importance they placed on 'relational factors

such as working with others, having good relationship and earning respect.' In general, relational factors were more important motivators for girls and for Hispanics and Blacks compared with Whites. The authors speculated that the latter may be related to differences in the norms and expectations of different communities. Marthen, Cees, Peter and Piet (2011) observed that due to limited data from developing countries, it was not easy to conduct a study on ethnic entrepreneurs; however, ethnic migration was a phenomenon one could easily find in most developing countries.

Goksel and Aydintan (2011) observed that migrants from rural areas preferred the formal sector, since jobs therein were considered to be prestigious, and they warrant a fixed income regardless of whether the work was long term or short term. But it was true that ethnic entrepreneurs or entrepreneurial migrants were a common phenomenon in developing countries. Ethnic entrepreneurs were characterized by small and medium businesses; they relied more on co-ethnic or family members as labour recruitment; they exercised control over a particular line of business; they had the tendency to live among fellow migrants, and contact with other group was restricted to business activities.

Marthen, et al (2011) observed that it was common that entrepreneurs in developing countries were dominated by a few ethnic groups. Skills were passed from one generation to another; from fellow migrants to each other, the skills were restricted within the group and in the future became the property of the group. The new migrants began work in the ethnic enterprise, but they later established their own businesses also within the boundary of the ethnic enterprise. This process may undergo several repeated steps until it eventually gave rise to chain migration. The first generation encouraged the second and the second encouraged the third and so forth, in order to reinforce the ethnic enclave in the receiving region.

Kiggundu (2002) reported that wherever society was highly differentiated along racial or ethnic lines, race and ethnicity have been used to predict entrepreneurial activity. Several studies have examined the relationship between racial differences and self-employment. Fairly (2004) reported that Black and Hispanic Americans exhibited lower rates of self-employment than other ethnic groups. Kollinger and Minniti (2006) however, showed that African Americans were more likely than either Hispanic Americans or Caucasian Americans to engage in entrepreneurial activities.

Kollinger and Minniti (2006) found that although Blacks were almost twice more likely to start a business than Whites, Blacks were significantly less likely than Whites to own and establish business that survived beyond the initial start-up. According to them, the gap in entrepreneurial propensity between Blacks and Whites could partly be explained by individual perceptions. High levels of confidence and optimistic

perceptions of entrepreneurship suggested that the subjective perceptions of Black Americans tend to be biased towards over-optimism more than the perceptions of Whites. Herrington, Kew and Kew (2010) reported that in South Africa, White and Indian/Asian individuals were more likely to start new business ventures than are Coloured or Black Africans. Giacomini, Jansen, Pruett, Shinnar, Llopis and Toney (2010) found that although students were motivated by similar factors and perceived similar barriers to creation, American, Asian and European students did not share the same entrepreneurial intentions or dispositions.

Duffy and Sedlacek (2007) found that African Americans and Asian Americans were more likely to express extrinsic values, while Whites were more likely to express intrinsic value. More specifically, Black adolescents tended to place a greater emphasis on social values whereas adolescent White men tended to favour work values focused on economic rewards and job security. Kiggundu (2002) concluded that differences in race and ethnicity might be indicative of other variables more important for entrepreneurial success.

3.2 Family business background and entrepreneurial venture choices

Wang and Wong (2004) stated that self-employed parents affected the entrepreneurial interest as well as the career choice of their children. There were two models to explain the family influence: parental role model and family support model. The parental role model asserted that persons with self-employed parents were more likely to start their own business due to the example of their parents. The family support model attributed this phenomenon to the financial or social support of their families. Thus it was expected to observe the positive correlation between entrepreneurial propensity and family income or social status. They tested the two models in Singapore on the influence of family background. Living in a city-state, Singapore income levels were largely measured by the type of housing they lived in (as a proxy). In general families living in small public houses were observed to be poorer than those living in large public houses or private houses. The test on the family support model could be done on the relationship between housing type of students and entrepreneurial aspiration. On the other hand, many self-employed persons were found to be small store owners and who may not be very wealthy. Thus, the correlation between income level and self-employed family was not very strong.

Sharma and Irving (2005) observed that the decision to join the family business as a career option was probably an alternative to pursuing entrepreneurial opportunities for oneself. This decision was important not only for the young people themselves, but also for their families and family businesses and society at large. It was

related to the extent of commitment to family business. Corroborating this view, Birley (2002) asserted that people with a higher level of education may have wider horizons and may not be willing to join the family firm. Sharma and Irving (2005) in a related development believed that the perception of substantial existing barriers to start a new business may have a positive influence on the decision to join the family firm, because of perceived lack of alternative entrepreneurial career opportunities.

Family capital refers to the totality of resources of the owning family members and has three components (human, social, and financial) (Danes, Stafford, Haynes & Amarapuskar, 2009). Research has shown that family social capital, described as non-financial resources and support offered by family members to the entrepreneur affected positively the start-up decision (Chang, Chrisman, Kellerman & Chau, 2009).

Basu and Virick (2008) reported that experiences during early childhood and socialization at home and in school probably shaped the attitudes of young people towards entrepreneurship. Ishfaq, Mohhammad, Zafar, Zeeshan, Armaid, Wasim-Ul and Naveed (2010) noted that family members in business became symbol for entrepreneurs and source of financial and non-financial helps; similarly financial resources in the family have direct bearing on entrepreneurial intentions. Students with intentions to become entrepreneurs were observed to be more qualified than non-entrepreneurial behaviour individuals. Landau (2007) believed that the family was a channel of culture and core cultural values, family background and relationships were even more fundamental to the understanding of initiation process and management of businesses. As a result, Rogoff and Heck (2003) stated that the business of entrepreneurship could not ignite and prosper without the mobilization of family forces.

Researchers have shown considerable interest in how family-owned business was transited (Carr & Sequeira, 2007); but not many researchers considered the role that family business background played in encouraging future engagement in entrepreneurship. Individuals from families with business background were likely to be aware of these impacts (Fairlie & Robb, 2005). This might spur them to incorporate their experiences, such that their attitude and behaviours towards entrepreneurial action were shaped towards nursing entrepreneurial intents. Having entrepreneurial parent enabled one to behave entrepreneurially and to work with higher entrepreneurial orientation than those whose parents were employment oriented (Ullah, Dean, & Kaleem, 2011). Wang and Wong (2004), Drennan, Kennedy and Renfrow (2005) in their different studies showed that students whose parents owned business demonstrated the highest preference of self-employment, some reported that family business had no influence on an individual's propensity to entrepreneurship (Goksel & Aydintan, 2011).

Drennan (2005) found that those who reported a positive view of their family's business experience perceived starting a business as both desirable and feasible. They found that other childhood experiences that involved facing adversity or frequent relocation also had a positive effect on individuals' perceived autonomy and attitude towards self-employment. At the same time, it could be argued that prior exposure in the form of direct experience in starting or attempting to start a new business could affect attitude and perceptions about entrepreneurship as a career (Ullah, Dean, & Kaleem (2011).

Researchers repeatedly showed that children who grew up with an entrepreneur parent had a greater propensity to choose an entrepreneurial career, whether in a patriarchal society (McElwee & Al-Riyami, 2003), a developing nation or a developed one (Schindehutte, Morris & Brennan, 2003). In a longitudinal study of small-business ownership, Mueller (2006) concluded that among the personal factors influencing a person's intent of an entrepreneurial career, the most important one remains parental role modelling.

Zellweger, Sieger and Helter (2010) stated that besides a peculiar familial context, by opting for succession, offspring also faced a particular organizational context in comparison to the founding or employment contents. For example, family firm and their senior managers often exhibited strong legacy concerns, sometimes accompanied by the inclination to tolerate under-performing activities because of family tradition. Offspring, then, may face strong inertial forces inhibiting timely and creative adaptations of the business portfolio (Sharma & Manikutty, 2005). To perpetuate continued family control, family firms tend to be more concerned about wealth preservation than wealth generation, thereby limiting the feasibility of bold entrepreneurial strategies.

Carney (2005) observed that governance structures were often personalized and focused on paternalistic family members. Rationally calculated decision criteria may be ignored, since control right permit the family to intervene in the affairs of the firm by substituting other, "particularistic" critical based upon altruism or nepotism, which may undermine the adoption of more objective and rationally calculated decision criteria that normally occur in the non-family context. Also, an owner-centric corporate culture, often impacted by the beliefs and fundamental motives of the founder, may limit a successor's room for discretion and may predetermine processes, behaviours, and decision-making routines.

In Singapore, Wang and Wong (2004) found that those showing more interest during programme on entrepreneurship were more likely to engage in entrepreneurship activity. The desire to study in entrepreneurship programmes was in

turn, found to be higher in people coming from families with business as major family occupation. Together, these suggest that family's occupational background is likely to impact the preferences of individuals towards entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship. In sum, students with family business background stem from a particular familial context may mould their future career intentions in the same pattern. When joining the family firm offspring have to deal with an organizational context that was often characterized by legacy concerns, person dependent governance structures and owner-centric organizational cultures.

4. Research Methodology

The study area is Cross River State and it is one of the oil-rich states in South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria. The state has 18 Local Government Areas and they have farming, fishing and trading as their major occupation. Calabar is the political and economic capital of the state.

4.1 Design

The design adopted for this study is survey. The choice of this design was predicated on the fact that the researchers were interested in ascertaining the nature of university students' demographic variables and their entrepreneurial business venture choices as at the time of this investigation.

4.2 Population of the study

The population of the study is 2,120 final year students of the faculties of Education, Social Sciences, Law, Arts and Medical Sciences of University of Calabar and 1,840 final year students of the faculties of Agriculture, Science, Management Sciences and Engineering of Cross River University of Technology both in Cross River State bringing the total population size to 3,960. The choice of final year students was based on the fact that they were already exposed to entrepreneurship development courses in their respective faculties and shall on graduation opt for self-employment.

4.3 Sampling technique

The technique adopted in selecting the sample for this study was stratified random sampling. Out of the 20 faculties (11 in University of Calabar; 9 in Cross River State University of Technology), 9 were randomly selected. The subjects that constituted the population were stratified into faculties.

With the use of simple random sampling, 44 students were selected from each of the 9 faculties using the hat and draw method. Subjects' entrepreneurial profiles were obtained from their Entrepreneurial Centres of the two universities. Numbers were assigned to the students' list on pieces of papers, rolled into balls and dropped into empty plastic can and shaken properly to ensure adequate mixture. Thereafter, the sample was blindly drawn where each number picked was recorded, folded and dropped back into the empty plastic can. This ensured that each student had equal independent opportunity of being drawn into the sample. Altogether 396 subjects formed sample size for the study.

4.4 Sample

The sample of this study consisted of 396 final year students drawn from the University of Calabar and Cross River University of Technology. They were made up of 44 students each drawn from the faculties of Education, Social Sciences, Law, Arts and Medical Sciences of the University of Calabar and Agriculture, Science, Management Sciences and Engineering from Cross River University of Technology.

4.5 Data collection

This was carried out with the use of a researcher-constructed instrument titled "Students' Demographics and Entrepreneurial Business Venture Choice Questionnaire (SDEBVCQ)". Section A of the instrument contained the demographics in respect of students' family background and their ethnic/geo-political background. Section B contained 40 items where 4 items were designed to measure each of the 10 students' business venture choices. The instrument was face-validated by 2 experts in Entrepreneurship Education, and 2 in Measurement and Evaluation. Reliability was established through a trial test involving 50 students who were not participants in the study. Cronbach Alpha method was used and reliability estimates of .76 to .83 were obtained indicating that the instrument was reliable to achieve this study's objectives.

The instrument was administered to the sampled students with the help of trained research assistants in the two universities. At the end of the exercise, all the instruments were retrieved giving a 100 percent returns rate. Contingency Chi-Square (χ^2) was used for data analysis.

5. Results

5.1 Hypothesis one

There is no significant influence of ethnic/geo-political background on entrepreneurial business venture choices of university students. The independent variable is ethnic/geo-political background while the dependent variable is entrepreneurial business venture choices of university students. The test statistic adopted in analyzing data for this hypothesis is Contingency Chi-Square (X^2). Summaries of the results are presented in table 1.

Table 1: Contingency Chi-square (X^2) analysis of the influence of ethnic/geo-political background on entrepreneurial business venture choices of university students

Entrepreneurial Business Venture choices		Ethnic/Geo-Political Background						Total	X^2
		South South	South East	South West	North East	North West	North Central		
Hairdressing	Observed	8	0	0	0	0	0	8	477.453
	Expected	(4.4)	(1.5)	(0.2)	(0.3)	(0.5)	(1.1)	(8.08)	
Photography	Observed	20	9	0	0	0	0	29	
	Expected	(16.1)	(5.4)	(.6)	(1.2)	(1.7)	(4.1)	(29.0)	
Computer repairs	Observed	32	0	0	8	0	0	40	
	Expected	(22.2)	(7.4)	(0.8)	(1.6)	(2.4)	(5.6)	(40.0)	
Interior decoration	Observed	25	8	0	0	0	24	57	
	Expected	(31.6)	(10.5)	(1.1)	(2.3)	(3.4)	(8.0)	(57.0)	
Bead making	Observed	0	0	0	0	8	0	8	
	Expected	(4.4)	(1.5)	(0.2)	(0.3)	(0.8)	(1.1)	(8.0)	
Fashion designing	Observed	76	17	0	8	0	16	117	
	Expected	(63.2)	(22.4)	(2.4)	(4.8)	(7.3)	(16.9)	(117.0)	
Bread baking	Observed	0	16	0	0	0	8	24	
	Expected	(13.3)	(4.4)	(0.5)	(1.0)	(1.4)	(3.4)	(24.0)	
Fish farming	Observed	33	8	0	0	16	8	65	
	Expected	(13.3)	(12.0)	(1.2)	(2.6)	(3.9)	(9.1)	(65.0)	
Electrical wiring	Observed	8	8	8	0	0	0	24	
	Expected	(13.3)	(4.4)	(0.5)	(1.0)	(1.4)	(3.4)	(24.0)	
Painting	Observed	16	8	0	0	0	0	24	
	Expected	(13.3)	(4.4)	(0.5)	(1.0)	(1.4)	(3.4)	(24.0)	
Total	Observed	218	74	8	16	24	56	396	
	Expected	(218.0)	(74.0)	(8.0)	(16.0)	(24.0)	(56.0)	(396.0)	

*Significant at .05 level; $df = 45$; critical $X^2 = 58.77$

Results of analysis in table 1 revealed that, the calculated X^2 value of 477.453 is greater than the critical X^2 value of 58.77 at .05 levels of significance with 45 degrees of freedom. This means that, there is a significant influence of ethnic/geo-political background on entrepreneurial business venture choices of university students.

Further observation of these results indicated that students from South-South who preferred Fashion designing were (76), followed by Fish farming (33), Computer repairs (32), Interior decoration (25), Photography (20), Painting (16), Hairdressing (8), Electrical wiring (8), Bead making (0) and Bread baking (0). Students from South-East preferred most Fashioning designing (17), Bread baking (16), Photography (9), Interior

decoration (8), Fish farming (8), Electrical wiring (8), Painting (8), Hairdressing (0), Computer repairs (0), and Bead making (0). Students from South-West only preferred Electrical wiring (8), while no other entrepreneurial business venture was preferred by them. Students from North-East preferred most Computer repairs (8), Fashion designing (8), no other entrepreneurial business venture was preferred by them. North-Western students preferred most Fish farming (16), followed by Bead making (8). They were not interested in other types of businesses. North-Central students preferred most Interior decoration (24), Fashion designing (16), Bread baking (8) and Fish farming (8).

Based on these results the null hypothesis was rejected, and so, there is a significant influence of ethnic/geo-political background on entrepreneurial business venture choices of university students.

Hypothesis two

There is no significant influence of family business background on entrepreneurial business venture choices of university students. The independent variable is family business background while the dependent variable is entrepreneurial business venture choices. The test statistic adopted for analyzing data for this hypothesis is Contingency Chi-Square (X^2). Summaries of the results are presented in table 2.

Table 2: Contingency Chi-square (X^2) analysis of the influence of family business background on entrepreneurial business venture choices of university students

Entrepreneurial Business Venture Choices		Family Business Background			Total	X^2
		None Members	1-3	All family Members		
Hairdressing	Observed	8	0	0	8	252.279*
	Expected	(1.8)	(5.4)	(.8)	(8.0)	
Photography	Observed	3	26	0	29	
	Expected	(6.6)	(19.5)	(2.9)	(29.0)	
Computer repairs	Observed	16	16	8	40	
	Expected	(9.1)	(26.9)	(4.0)	(40.0)	
Interior decoration	Observed	0	57	0	57	
	Expected	(31.0)	(38.3)	(5.7)	(57.0)	
Bead making	Observed	0	0	8	8	
	Expected	(1.8)	(5.4)	(0.8)	(8.0)	
Fashion designing	Observed	40	65	16	121	
	Expected	(27.5)	(81.4)	(12.1)	(121.0)	
Bread baking	Observed	16	0	8	24	
	Expected	(5.5)	(16.1)	(2.4)	(24.0)	
Fish farming	Observed	0	61	0	61	
	Expected	(14.8)	(39.7)	(6.5)	(61.0)	
Electrical wiring	Observed	0	24	0	65	
	Expected	(5.5)	(16.1)	(2.4)	(65.0)	
Painting	Observed	8	16	0	24	
	Expected	(5.5)	(16.1)	(2.4)	(24.0)	
Total	Observed	91	265	40	396	
	Expected	(91.0)	(265.0)	(40.0)	(396.0)	

*Significant at .05 level; $df = 18$; critical $X^2 = 28.87$

Results of the analysis in table 2 revealed that, the calculated Contingency Chi-square (X^2) value of 252.279 is greater than the critical X^2 value of 28.87 at .05 levels of significance with 18 degrees of freedom. This means that, there is a significant influence of family business background on entrepreneurial business venture choice of university students.

Further examination of the results showed that students whose family members did not have any business background preferred most Fashion designing (40), followed by Computer repairs (16), Bread baking (16), Hairdressing (8), Painting (8), and Photography (3). Students who had 1-3 members of their family in business preferred most Fashion designing (65), Fish farming (61), Interior decoration (57), Photography (26), Electrical wiring (24), Computer repairs (16), and Painting (16). Those students whose all family members owned business preferred most Fashion designing (16), Computer repair (8), Bead making (8), and Bread baking (8). Other entrepreneurial business ventures were not considered by these classes of students.

By these results, the null hypothesis was rejected, and so, there is a significant influence of family business background on entrepreneurial business choice of university students.

6. Discussion of findings

A. Influence of geo-political/ethnic background on entrepreneurial business venture choices

The results in table 1 showed that there is a significant influence of geo-political/ethnic background on entrepreneurial business venture choices of university students. With this result, the null hypothesis was rejected and in its place, the alternate hypothesis subsists. This finding means that a geo-political zone a person hails from is likely to influence such a person's venture, career and occupational choices. It is therefore not unusual to come across a prospective entrepreneur who simply chose a business venture because his/her kinsmen or tribal people are in that line of business, not because of his/her inclination towards it.

A plausible explanation for this finding might be that Nigeria as a country is divided along geo-political and ethnic lines, where each group desires to have supremacy over others. So, the quest for superiority over others can ginger a prospective entrepreneur to choose a business venture where his/her tribesmen have an edge over others. Closely akin to this articulation is the need to receive assistance from fellow tribesmen which is necessary if such prospective entrepreneur is to succeed in his/her choice of business venture. The belief is that people from the same geo-political

or ethnic background are likely to exhibit strong desire to assist their own to succeed in any business venture they are well established in, with the hope that any success recorded may be for the good and well-being of their area. So success in business is likely to be used for the development of their area.

This result is in conformity with Kiggundu (2002) who reported that wherever society was highly differentiated along racial or ethnic lines, race and ethnicity have been used to predict entrepreneurial activity. In support, Marthen, et al (2011) observed that it is common that entrepreneurs in developing countries were dominated by a few ethnic groups. Skills were passed from one generation to another, from fellow migrants to each other; the skills were restricted within the group and in the future became the property of the group. Ethnic groups were culture-bearing units and common group values were major contributors to a sense of identity and to peculiar ways of perceiving, thinking, feeling, and behaving that influenced action in everyday life (Chan & Lee, 2004; Hanson, 2004), including entrepreneurial intent and the actual entrepreneurial behaviour. Entrepreneurial activity in many societies was heavily influence by cultural practices. It therefore follows that entrepreneurial venture choice among university students could be swayed by their ethnic/geopolitical background, irrespective of the entrepreneurial education programme of study they underwent in their institutions.

B. Influence of family business background on entrepreneurial business venture choice

Results displayed in table 2 showed that there is a significant influence of family business background on entrepreneurial business venture choice of university students. This finding suggests that family business background can sway a potential entrepreneur's interest to pursue the same business. This is usually the case where a family business records outstanding success and has spanned over large spheres of operation. The desire to identify with success or be a part of a successful team has the tendency to motivate an aspiring entrepreneur towards embracing family business.

This finding is not surprising. Nigerians have a habit of desiring their children to take after them in their businesses or other human endeavours. It is common place to witness a business man ensuring that at least one of his/her children; no matter how many they are, is trained and encouraged to tow the parent's line of business for perpetuity purposes. Ditto for lawyers, accountants, medical doctors, academics, educationists, engineers and so on. This reinforces the age-long tradition of reproducing oneself by ensuring that there is a worthy successor for whatever art or trade a family is renowned for. Thus, a founder of a venture may die, but such ventures survive to continue with the legacies left behind.

This result is in consonance with Wang and Wong (2004) who stated that self-employed parent affected the entrepreneurial interest as well as the career choice of their children. It is therefore not out of place to assert that persons with self-employed parents were more likely to start their own business due to the example of their parents. This could be replicated in families.

In support of this finding also is Zellweger's (2010) report that beside a peculiar familial context, by opting for succession, offspring also faced a particular organizational context in comparison to the founding of employment contexts. For example, family firms and their senior managers often exhibited strong legacy concerns, sometimes accompanied by the inclination to tolerate underperforming activities because of family tradition.

In all, family business background is a strong motivator of university students in their choice of entrepreneurial business venture. Students, indeed, every human being desire success for their families and are ready to work towards this. So, where a family has made name in business, their offspring are likely to preserve the legacy by choosing the same line of business, with the hope that as family business succeeds, theirs will follow suit. It is therefore not common to observe a young entrepreneur deviating from a family's line of business, especially if it is a successful one to entirely strange venture. So this finding is in line with common belief and articulation among people that family legacies must be perpetuated by indulging in any business venture such a family is noted for.

7. Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that entrepreneurial business venture choices were not made in isolation but under very significant influence of certain demographic variables. These variables were; their ethnic/geo-political background and their family business background. Thus, the ability of students to make informed business venture choices stemmed from their exposure to ethnic/geo-political, family business backgrounds and participating in entrepreneurship education programme in the universities as an instrument for self-employment generation and wealth creation.

7.1 Implications for management effectiveness

For the fact that ethnic/geo-political background has significant influence on entrepreneurial business venture choices of university students implies that ethnic/geo-political background is a factor to be given consideration in entrepreneurship

education. Management of entrepreneurship education should therefore integrate ethnic/geopolitical factors in the programme. To succeed in this, business ventures peculiar to various ethnic/geopolitical zones should be identified and students from such areas encouraged to show interest in them, with a view to opting for them upon their graduation. It is believed that students who choose business ventures along the ethnic/geopolitical lines are likely to excel in them because of language power and familiarity with the areas.

The significant influence of family business background on entrepreneurial business choice of university students implies that knowledge and participation in family business by university students can boost entrepreneurship education. That is, students can bring in their wealth of experience from participating in family business and share with their colleagues and coordinators of entrepreneurship education. This can improve entrepreneurship education. Therefore, family business should be incorporated in entrepreneurship education programme where students can be encouraged to share the success story of their family business ventures. With this, cross fertilization of ideas are guaranteed.

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